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Search for sub-millicharged particles at J-PARC

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Abstract

Electric charge quantization is a long-standing question in particle physics. While fractionally charged particles, millicharged particles hereafter, have typically been thought to preclude the possibility of Grand Unified Theories, well-motivated dark-sector models have been proposed to predict the existence of millicharged particles while preserving the possibility for unification. Such models can contain a rich internal structure, providing candidate particles for dark matter. A number of experiments have searched for millicharged particles χ s, but in the parameter space of the charge Q and mass m_χ , the region of $m_\chi > 0.1 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $Q < 10^{-3}$ is largely unexplored. SUB-Millicharge ExperimentT has been proposed to search for sub-millicharged particles using 30 GeV proton fixed-target collisions at J-PARC. The detector is composed of two layers of stacked scintillator bars and photomultiplier tubes, and is proposed to be installed 280 m from the target. The main background is expected to be a random coincidence between the two layers due to dark counts in photomultiplier tubes and the radiation from the surrounding materials, which can be reduced significantly using the timing of the proton beam. With $N_{\text{POT}} = 5 \times 10^{21}$, the experiment provides sensitivity to χ s with the charge down to $8 \times 10^{-5}e$ in $m_\chi < 0.2 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $10^{-3}e$ in $m_\chi > 1.6 \text{ GeV}/c^2$. This is the regime largely uncovered by the previous experiments.

1 Introduction

Quantization of electric charge (Q) remains as one of the pivotal yet unresolved questions in elementary particle physics. The emergence of well-grounded dark sector models suggests the potential existence of millicharged particles. Intriguingly, these models often exhibit intricate internal structures, positioning them as prospective candidates for dark matter. Consequently, the presence of fractionally charged particles could signify a monumental leap beyond the boundaries of the standard model.

A straightforward augmentation to the standard model entails incorporating an additional $U(1)$ gauge into the dark sector. Under the premise that a new $U(1)$ gauge boson exists (referred to as the dark photon A'), and there exists a kinematic mix between the dark photon and the Standard Model photon B , it implies that the dark fermion (χ) can potentially interact with B [1, 2]. This interaction posits that the charge of the χ is proportional to the size of the mixing, thereby yielding a fractional electric charge of the dark fermion.

This article describes the concept of the SUB-Millicharge Experiment (SUBMET) and its status. The SUBMET has been proposed [3] to investigate the presence of millicharged particles (χ s) using the 30 GeV proton beam at the Japan Proton Accelerator Research Complex (J-PARC). The detector design and the structure of the J-PARC beam allow the experiment to probe the low mass ($< 1 \text{ MeV}/c^2$) and low charge ($Q < 10^{-3}e$) regime that remains uncharted by previous experiments. In particular, the projected sensitivity shows that the experiment could detect particles with charge as small as $Q < 8 \times 10^{-5}e$ for $m_\chi < 0.2 \text{ GeV}/c^2$.

2 Related Works

Figure 1: The existing exclusion limits on m_χ and $\epsilon = Q/e$ [4].

Various experiments have searched for millicharged particles and the effort spans a diverse range of methodologies and settings:

- Electron fixed-target experiments [5].
- Proton-proton collider experiments [6, 7, 8].
- Proton fixed-target experiments [4].

- Neutrino-based experiments [9, 10].

For a more in-depth exploration of these experimental endeavors, readers are directed to the comprehensive review presented in Ref. [11]. A notable observation from these collective efforts is a gap in our investigative reach. Specifically, the domain where $m_\chi > 0.1 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $Q < 10^{-3}e$ remains largely unexplored, which is conspicuously illustrated in Figure 1.

3 Detection Efficiency Study: LED Test

The detection of millicharged particles relies on the effective combination of a photomultiplier tube (PMT) with a scintillator. The role of a scintillator is to convert particle interactions into detectable light signals. Given that millicharged particle interactions often yield only a few scintillation photons, and frequently just a single photon, a sensitive detection system is essential.

To evaluate the detection capability of the system, an LED test was set up. In this test, a PMT was positioned inside a dark box to shield it from external light sources. An LED was placed directly in front of the photocathode of the PMT. Using a function generator, a small electric signal was introduced to the LED, simulating the faint light signals expected from millicharged particle interactions with the scintillator. Within this controlled setting, the PMT showed a high detection efficiency ($\sim 99.5\%$) of the single-photoelectric signals.

The outcomes of the LED test provide evidence for the suitability of the SUBMET experimental design in detecting millicharged particles.

4 Principle of Experiment

4.1 Experimental Setup

Figure 2: Illustration of the experimental site. χ s are produced near the target and reach SUBMET after penetrating the beam dump, the muon monitor, and the sand.

The SUBMET detectors tailored for the detection of sub-millicharged particles. At the core of the system lies the combination of a PMT with a scintillator, optimized for high sensitivity due to the characteristic faint signals from interactions with millicharged particles.

The experiment employs a 30 GeV proton beam provided by J-PARC, which is directed toward a fixed target. As a consequence of these proton fixed-target collisions, various neutral mesons can be generated, acting as potential sources for millicharged particle production. Specifically, light mesons such as π^0 , η decay through an intermediate photon, which can then lead to the production of millicharged particles. Conversely, heavier mesons, like ρ , ω , ϕ and J/ψ have the capability to decay directly into a pair of χ s. The SUBMET detector, positioned 280-meters from the target, is strategically placed to capture potential signals from these millicharged particle interactions. The experimental site is illustrated in Figure 2.

4.2 Detector Design

The SUBMET detector has been designed to use long modules to maximize interaction possibilities within limited space. It consists of the following components:

- Scintillator bars: these materials are sensitive to incoming particle interactions and produce a flash of light (scintillation) when a particle passes through them. The size is $5 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm} \times 1500 \text{ mm}$.
- Photomultiplier tubes (PMTs): positioned in close proximity to the scintillator bars, the PMTs are tasked with detecting the faint light emitted from the scintillator. Their design ensures the amplification of this faint signal (even SPE signal) into an easily detectable electric signal.
- Module and supermodule: one module consists of a PMT, a scintillator, and a structure that helps combine the PMT and the scintillator. The 2×2 modules are again combined into one supermodule to facilitate installation and management. Supermodules are placed one by one in a grid-shaped cage made of aluminum.
- Dual-layer structure: the detector consists of two separate layers of stacked scintillator bars and PMTs as shown in Figure 3. This configuration is pivotal for differentiating genuine signals from background noise. The expectation is that a real millicharged particle interaction will create coincident signals in both layers.
- Alignment and positioning: the axis of the detector is aligned to the target direction to maximize the chances of capturing interactions of χ s. The extended distance through sand and rocks following the target collision acts as a filter, primarily allowing low-interaction particles like neutrinos to penetrate. This may also include potential millicharged particles.

4.3 Backgrounds

Managing and reducing background are essential for the success of the SUBMET experiment. The experiment employs a two-layer design to differentiate between genuine millicharged particle signals and background noise. A genuine signal is expected to produce coincident signals in both layers. This dual-layer setup, combined with the synchronization of the detection system with timing of the proton beam, provides a robust mechanism to minimize false detections. Genuine millicharged particle interactions are more likely to produce simultaneous signals in both layers, allowing for higher confidence in detection and a significant reduction in false positives.

5 Current Status

The design of the mechanical system has been developed with an emphasis on seismic safety, ensuring that the entire setup is robust against potential seismic disturbances. Currently, efforts are concentrated on the assembly phase, wherein all components are integrated to form a cohesive system. Concurrently, tests are being conducted to verify that the system operates within the specified requirements of the experiment.

The assembly process of these modules is in progress, with each module undergoing tests to assess its functionality and reliability under the intended experimental conditions.

The pivotal readout system, responsible for capturing and transmitting data from the detector, is being developed using the DRS4 sampler chip [12]. The readout system is being developed and manufactured by NOTICE Korea [13] and, in parallel, tests are underway to evaluate the system's precision and efficiency.

Figure 3: Illustration of the SUBMET detector. A module is composed of a $50 \times 50 \times 1500 \text{ mm}^3$ scintillator bar and a PMT, and 2×2 modules form a supermodule. 5×4 supermodules are stacked together in a layer. The stacked supermodules are covered by scintillator panels. Two layers of the stack are aligned such that a χ (red line) penetrates both layers in a narrow time window.

6 Timeline and Milestones

The SUBMET experiment has progressed through various milestones and has a clear roadmap for the future. Here's a chronological account of the key events and anticipated steps:

- Summer 2020: Letter of Intent (LOI) was submitted.
- Summer 2021: The proposal was presented at the 32nd Program Advisory Committee (PAC) meeting.
- April 2022: The project received Stage-1 approval.
- November 2022: The Technical Design Report (TDR) was submitted.
- December 2022: Facility Integration and Funding Committee (FIFC) was held.
- January 2023: At the 35th PAC meeting, a request for Stage-II approval was made.
- **June 2023 (current): The project received Stage-2 (final) approval.**
- Fall 2023: The installation phase begins, with all components and systems being integrated at the designated site.
- Spring 2024: Data-taking is scheduled to start, marking the active phase of the experiment.

7 Conclusions

The SUBMET experiment at J-PARC aims to advance the search for millicharged particles, focusing on $m_\chi > 0.1 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $Q < 10^{-3}e$ region. Since the submission of the LOI in summer 2020, the project has adhered to a structured progression, highlighting the importance of detector design and effective background reduction. With installation set for Fall 2023 and data-taking in Spring 2024, the result of the search could provide pivotal insights into charge quantization.

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